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An Assessment of Post-Harvest Loss of Onion Farmers in Wamakko LGA of Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Most of the farmers in Wamakko local government area bring onions directly to the market after harvest as proper storage facilities are not available with them. It is against this, farmers usually unload their entire stock within a month of harvest, during which prices are very low thereby making them to be at the last receiving end. The objective of this research is to identify the causes of onions post-harvest losses, indigenous technologies used for Onion storage in the study area and to present possible recommendations based on the findings of the study. Mixed methods were employed through the use of a structured questionnaire encompassing both open and close ended questions as well interview. Data for the study were generated from both primary and secondary sources from sample population of 240 farmers in four major onion producing areas. The primary data for the study was obtained from onion farmers using pre-test structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered through face-to-face interviews with farmers. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to analyze the data. The study reveals that the most important factor in onion storage with almost 79% is inadequate storage facilities. It also indicated that the present storage structure is using local storage (rumbu and dabi) and spreading on mud floor in a room and under tree shade. The study recommends that government and private organization should assist farmers with modern storage structures to avoid economic loss of onion.

Keywords: Onions; Wamakko; Post harvest losses; farmers

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Onion (*Allium cepa L.*) is a herbaceous biennial plants belonging to the family *Amaryllidacea* and genus *Allium* (Grubben *et al.*, 2004). Bulb onion also known as common onion is grown globally as a commercial crop and is used as widely either as a vegetable in form of a salad or as a component in a meal preparation. Onion is a source of vitamin c, vitamin B6, potassium, magnesium polyphenols, and its medicinal value is highly acclaimed (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2003; Hanninen *et al.*, 2000; Verma and Singh, 2004).

Onion is grown globally in about 170 countries. China ranks the first with over 18 million tons of bulb onion produced, followed by India (11 million) and USA (about 3.2 millions) tons annual production (Hanci, 2018).

Nigeria is the largest producer of onion in West Africa with a total production of slightly above 1.1 million tonnes. Onions are mostly produced in the Northern Nigeria. The dominant states involved in the production of onions are Sokoto, Kaduna, and Kano States (CBI, 2021).

In the meantime, while the number of food insecure population remains unacceptably high, each year and worldwide, massive quantities of food are lost due to spoilage and infestations on the journey to costumers (FAO, 2010). In some African countries like Nigeria, where tropical weather and poorly developed infrastructure contribute to the problem, post-harvest loss can regularly be as high as 40-50% (IFAD, 2012). Obviously, one of the strengthening food qualities and quantity is by reducing these losses.

Annually, farmers produce a lot to boost the economy but most are lost at post-harvest stages. Thus, outputs of all agricultural commodities produced in the field have to undergo series operations such as threshing, transportation, processing, storage and exchange before reaching the final consumer and there are appreciable losses of outputs during the stages of handling (Basavaraja *et al.*, 2006). The sum quantity of outputs lost in these stages is referred to as ‘‘ post harvest losses’’. The post harvest scenario in vegetables (onions) present a dismal picture of and are mostly comprise of traditional techniques practiced by growers resulting in a considerable deterioration of physical and nutritional qualities of the harvested crop (Oni and Obiakor, 2002; Sablani *et al.*, 2002; Alidu *et al.*, 2016). Olayemi *et al.*, (2012) pointed out that the quality and nutritional worth of the fresh foods is affected by post harvest handling and storage conditions that eventually causes post harvest losses. Mrema and Rolle (2002) also stated that post harvest losses of onion ranges between 20-40%, because harvesting, processing/storage techniques are inefficient, as a result, supply is unstable. In perishable crops like onion, proper and scientific storage, packaging, transport and handling technologies are not adequate and hence, considerable amount of produce is wasted. The moisture content of the onion is inherently more liable for deterioration in quality and quantity especially under tropical conditions. Moreover, they are biologically active and carry out transpiration, respiration, and other biochemical activities that contribute for deterioration in quality of the produce. Thus, post harvest losses in onions during post harvest operations due to improper handling and storage are enormous. Basavaraja *et al.*, (2006) reported that in underdeveloped and developing tropical countries, both quantitative and qualitative losses of agricultural products occur at all stages in the post harvest value chain, from harvesting, through handling, storage, processing, packaging transportation and marketing until crops are delivered to final consumers.

Post harvest losses in onions can be caused by a wide variety of factors/determinants ranging from poor sources of planting seeds/seedlings, growing conditions, to handling at a farm level. Not only are losses clearly a waste of food, but also represent a similar waste of human efforts, farm inputs, livelihoods, investments and scarce resources such as water (Olayemi *et al.*, 2012).

In Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State where Onion is grown in large quantity mostly during the dry season with inadequate storage capacities that are mostly traditional and unscientific. As a result, during this period prices rule very low due to glut situation. Thereafter, the rise in prices is quite rapid and sometimes wide fluctuations occur leading to dissatisfaction amongst the producers as well as consumers. During this bulk production period, onion growers either sell their produce at low price in fear of high storage loss or store for a few days using traditional methods under ambient environment. In both cases, dealers have more control of onion price in favor of the growers because of poor or unavailability of storage facilities such as cold storage and where they are available they are beyond the reach of small holder farmers. These necessitate most of the farmers in Wamakko Local Government Area to bring their onion directly to the market after harvest in order to avoid post-harvest loss. Mrema and Rolle, (2002) posited that about 20-40% of Onion are losses after Post-harvest due to inefficient storage techniques. This is similar to Salisu *et al.*, (2019) that stated 31% and above onion loss occurred as result of inadequate and local storage techniques. This research intends to identify the causes of onions post-harvest losses incurred by the farmers and indigenous technologies used for Onion storage with the view to find the possible solutions and recommendations of the post harvest loss incurred by the

onion farmers. Thus, this study will focus on to assess the post harvest losses of onion farmers in Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria, which lies between latitude 12° N and 13° 58 N and longitude 04° 8' E and 6° 54 E. Wamakko was estimated to have an area of 697km² and a population of 209,204 (National Population Census, 2015). Wamakko Local Government Area was described by the presence of hills, sandy savannah, in addition to numerous rivers, streams and dams. The annual rainfall is about 50mm with the highest peak in August. The predominant tribe in Wamakko is Hausa. The residents were mainly farmers and fishermen (Kabiru et al., 2013).

Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Map of Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State

Data for the study were generated from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data for the study was obtained from onion farmers, by using pre-test structured questionnaire. The data collected include the causes of onion losses, and the indigenous onion storage methods used and possible solutions and recommendations. The questionnaires were administered through face-to-face interviews with farmers.

The population of the study consist of the Onion farmers in the four (4) major onion production communities of Wamakko Local Government area, such as Asari, Lokobi mana, Gidan Kaduna and Fanari village in which 240 farmers were selected for the study. The data collected for the study were conducted from September 2nd to 26th October, 2024 using questionnaires techniques in order to facilitate a better understanding of the data generated in the research process with the help research

assistants. The data obtained from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics with the help of Microsoft Excel.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Causes of Postharvest Loss

The result from the data obtained on the causes of Post harvest loss in the study area indicated that, all the onion farmers' experiences post harvest loss, table 1.

Table 1: Farmers Experiences in Post harvest Losses

	Asari	%	Lokobi Mana	%	Gidan kaduna	%	Fanari	%	Total	%
Yes	60	100	60	100	60	100	60	100	240	100
No	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	60		60		60		60		240	100

Field Survey; 2024

The most important factors that are responsible for post-harvest loss are animals (rodents, rat and insect) (19.24%) inadequate storage facilities (78.58%) and negligible contributions of inappropriate transportation facilities (2.18%) as indicated below;

Fig 2: Factors Responsible for Post harvest Loss in the Study Area.

Inadequate storage facilities were recorded to be the highest causes of post harvest loss in the area. This incidence makes the farmers to incur loss in economic terms. Some of the respondents revealed that, out of hundred (100) bags of onion stored after harvesting is hardly to get thirty (40) bags in a year. This necessitate some farmers to sell their products immediately after harvesting at farm point or to market directly

3.2 Indigenous Methods of Onion Storage Facility

The Onion farmers in the study area adopt various methods of storing the onion such as local store (Rumbu), Local store (Dabi), spreading on the mud floor inside room and spreading under tree in order

to avoid post harvest losses. And each method use depends on the ability and capability of the individual farmer as indicated in table 2. Majority of the respondents (52.91%) in the study area use local store (rumbu) as a means of storing their Onion product. This method indicates lower risk of post harvest loss and therefore highly adopted indigenous method of storing onion product in the study area.

Table 2. Indigenous (Local) Method Used for Onion Storage in the Study Area

	Asari	%	Lokobi mana	%	Gidan kaduna	%	Fanari	%	Total	%
Local store(rumbu)	32	53	30	50	30	50	35	58	127	52.91
Local store(Dabi)	18	30	25	41.6	20	33.3	15	25	78	32.5
Spreading on the mud floor inside room	7	11.66	3	5	5	8.33	5	8.3	20	8.33
Spreading under tree	3	5	2	3.33	5	8.33	5	8.3	15	6.25
Total	60	100	60	100	60	100	60	100	240	100

Field survey; 2024.

The rate of Onion loss incurs at storage duration as indicated by farmers between 31% and above of the total Onion produce by farmers is (61.25%) in all the sampled areas of the study area with the exception of very few farmers (12.5%) that experiences about 1-10% loss of the Onion (table 3) as a results of unscientific method of storage facilities used as spreading on a mud inside the room and spreading under the tree shade.

Table 3. Rate of Onion Loss Incur at Storage in the Study Area.

Rate	Asari	%	Lokobi mana	%	Gidan kaduna	%	Fanari	%	Total	%
1-10%	0	00.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
11-20%	9	15	3	5	12	20	6	10	30	12.5
21-30%	18	30	12	20	24	40	9	15	63	26.25
31% and above	33	55	45	75	24	40	45	75	147	61.25
Total	60	100	60	100	60	100	60	100	240	100

Field survey; 2024

But in some places like Khartoum state, farmers are using open places, under trees shade, or huts as their storage facilities with storage loss estimated to be 2% to 80% with an average of 29% (Abdallah and Ahmed, 2015)

4.0: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusion

Data obtained on the causes of Post harvest loss in the area indicated that, all the onion farmers' experiences post harvest loss. This post harvest loss is caused by Animals (rodents, rat and insect) (19.24%), Inadequate storage facilities (78.58%) and negligible contribution of inappropriate transportation facilities (2.18%). Inadequate storage facilities were recorded to be the highest causes of post harvest loss in the area. This incidence makes the farmers to incur loss in economic terms. Some of the respondents revealed that, out of hundred (100) bags of onion stored after harvesting is hardly to get forty (40) bags in a year. This necessitates some farmers to sell their products immediately after

harvesting at farm point or to market directly. The high rate of post harvest loss in the study area necessitate the farmers to adopt various methods of storing the onion such as local store (Rumbu), Local store (Dabi), spreading on the mud floor inside room and spreading under tree in order to avoid post harvest losses. And each method use depends on the ability and capability of the individual farmer as indicated in table 2. Majority of the respondents (52.91%) in the study area use local store (rumbu) as a means of storing their Onion product. This method indicates lower risk of post harvest loss and therefore highly adopted indigenous method of storing onion product in the study area.

The rate of Onion loss incurs at storage duration post harvest as indicated by farmers/cultivars is between 31% and above of the total Onion produce by farmers (61.25%) in all the sampled areas of the study area with the exception of very few farmers (12.5%) that experiences about 1-10% loss of the Onion as a results of unscientific method of storage facilities used as spreading on a mud inside the room and spreading under the tree shade.. But, the use of the traditional and unscientific method of storing Onion in the area makes the Onion to suffer greatly from weight loss and loss in economic/financial value as a result of inadequate ventilation spaces and absorption of heat by the surrounding environs during the day.

4.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the findings of the study, it was recommended that;

1. There is need for the government and private Organization to provide assistance to the farmers in order to build modern Onion Storage facilities so as to avoid post harvest loss.
2. Considering the nutritional value of Onion, there is need for the government and private Organizations/Individuals to provide Onion Processing plant that can be used for different purposes apart from food.

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REFERENCES

- Abdalla, I. and Ahmed, M. M., (2015). Study of Value chains of Onion Production and Marketing in Khartoum State. Natural Resources, Agricultural Development and Food Security: International Research Network. International Working Paper Series, Paper Number 15/11. Retrieved on 4th August, 2018 <http://economia.unipv.it/naf/>
- Alidu, A., Ali, E. B., Aminu, H. (2016). Determinants of Post-Harvest Losses Among Tomato Farmers in the Navrongo Municipality in the Upper East Region, Ghana. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare* 6(12): 14-20.
- Basavaraja, H., Mahajanashetti, S.B. and Udagatti, N. C. (2007). Economic Analysis of Post- Harvest Losses in Food Grains in India: A Case Study of Karnataka. *Agric. Econ. Res. Rev.* 20: 117-126.
- Centre for the Promotion of Imports from Developing Countries (CBI), (2021). Food Loss in Nigeria: Value Chain Analysis of Tomato, Onion, and Chilli Value Chains. Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Nigeria, Surechain. PP10-82.
- Dogondaji, S. D. (2005). Economics of Dry season Production and Marketing in Sokoto and kebbi States, Nigeria. A PhD thesis Submitted to the Dept of Agricultural economics, Faculty of Agriculture, UDUS, PP1-45.
- Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nation (FAO), (2010):

www.Faostat.vegetable.onion/Data. Retrieved 28/07/2017

- Gathambambiri, C. W., Mbaka, J. N. And Owino W. O, (2021) Postharvest Losses of Bulb Onion (*Allium Cepa L.*) in Selected Sub- Counties of Kenya in *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 2021; **21**(2) 17529- 17544.
- Grubben, M. C., Denton, G.J.H. and Schippers, R. R. (2004) Plant Resources of Tropical Africa Vegetables. PROTA Foundation, Wageningen, Netherlands, Backhuys Publishers, Leiden, Netherlands CTA, 2004.
- Hanninen, L. J., Kaartinen, K., Rauma, A. L., Nenonen, M., and Adlercreutz, H. (2018). Antioxidants in Vegan Diet and Rheumatic Disorders Toxicology. 2000; (155)1–3:45–53.
- Hanci, F. A. (2018). Comprehensive Overview of Onion Production: Worldwide and *Turkey J. Agric. Vet. Sci.* 2018; **11** (9):17–27.
- International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), (2012) The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2012: Economic Growth Necessary to Accelerate Reduction of Hunger and Malnutrition. Rome: FAO; 2014.P5.
- Kabiru, M., Ikeh, E. I., Aziah, I., Julia, O., Fabiyi, J. P., & Mohammed, R. A. (2013). Prevalence and intensity of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection. A community based survey among school children and adult in Wamakko town, Sokoto State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health*, 2(1), 12–22.
- Mrema, C.G. and S.R. Rolle, (2002). Status of Postharvest Sector and its Contribution to Agricultural Development and Economic Growth. Proceeding of the 9th JIRCAS International Symposium, (JIRCAS'08), Value-Addition to Agricultural Products, Ibaraki, Japan, pp: 13-20.
- Mbuk, E. M., Basse, N. E., Udoh, E. S. & Udoh, E.J. (2011). Factors Influencing Post- Harvest Loss of Tomato in Urban Market in Uyo, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Agriculture, Food and Environment*. **7**(2): 40-46.
- National Population Census (2015). Projected population, 2015–2020. Sokoto: National Population Commission Office.
- Oni, K.C. and S.I. Obiakor, (2002). Post Harvest Food Loss Prevention: The role of the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) Ilorin under the FGN/UNDP first country Cooperation (ccf-1) Framework. Proceedings of National Seminar for Cooperating Agencies Under the CCF- I Framework on Post Harvest Food Loss Prevention, April 18-19, Ibadan, pp: 1-10
- Olayemi F. F., Adegbola J. A., Bamishaiye E. I. and Daura A. M. (2010), Assessment of post-harvest challenges of Small Scale Farm Holders of Tomatoes, Bell and Hot Pepper in Some Local Government Areas of Kano State Nigeria, p.39.
- Sablani, S.S., Opara, L.U. and Al-Balushi, K. (2006). Influence of Bruising and Storage Temperature on Vitamin C Content of Tomato. *Journal of Food, Agriculture and Environment* **4**(1): 54 - 56.
- Salisu, L. H., Aliyu, S. M., and Zaharau, I. U. (2019). An Assessment of Onion Post Harvest Loss in Desert Prone Line of Kano State, Nigeria. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare* **9** (4): 44-47.
- Verma, A. and Singh, K.P. (2004). An Economic Analysis of Post-Harvest Losses in Fresh Vegetables. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Marketing*, **18**(1): 136-139.
- Rodrigues, A. S., Graziani, G. and Fogliano, V. (2003). Nutritional Value of Onion Regional Varieties in Northwest Portugal Electron. *J. Environ. Agric. Food Chem.* 2003; **4** (2):519–524.